

In November 2023, members of the [Birth Companions Lived Experience Team](#) came together with maternity researchers from the [University of Birmingham](#) to discuss experiences of participating in maternity research, and what women facing acute inequity and disadvantage might need in order to feel safe sharing their lived experience with academic researchers.

This is what we learned.

What do women need in order to feel comfortable getting involved in maternity research?

1. Information and transparency
2. Advance notice
3. Flexibility
4. Multiple ways to be involved
5. Trusted relationships
6. Safe spaces
7. Clear purpose and value to work
8. Feeling included, genuinely supported, and cared for
9. Checking in before and after
10. Follow up

Why do women get involved in maternity research?

1. To create change
2. To help other women
3. To make your voice heard
4. A desire to 'give back'

What are the barriers to getting involved in maternity research?

1. Trauma and anxiety
2. Lack of safe, pre-existing relationships
3. Childcare
4. Uncertainty around next steps and outcomes

Recruitment: Considerations for maternity researchers

1. Recruitment via social media
2. Recruitment via posters/flyers in medical settings
3. Recruitment via trusted organisations

What do women need in order to feel comfortable getting involved in maternity research?

1. Information and transparency

Information provided must be detailed, complete and transparent in order for women to make informed choices about participation.

"So that's like the transparency. You will know what it's about, then you know if you're interested or not, but you've already been given all the information. There's nothing hidden."

2. Advance notice

Dates and plans must be shared well in advance to allow women to make all necessary arrangements. (e.g. travel, childcare).

"The notice that we get is important. We know about all these events prior, way prior, to it. So you can make any arrangements, like if you have to deal with any childcare."

3. Flexibility

Options for participation must be made as broad and flexible as possible, (e.g. by running the same session on multiple dates and at different times, and being adaptable to our individual needs).

"There was groups that we've had two or three different dates that would be available, for everyone to take part. So you always feel included."

4. Multiple ways to be involved

Women must be offered opportunities to share their experiences using a wide variety of methods and formats (e.g., face to face, via online chat, email or phone).

"I think that's it's a big thing, especially when people are talking about their trauma and things that they've been through, sometimes you might sit there and think "I don't really wanna share that." But then we always have the option, if there's something she doesn't want to share in front of people, she can always email afterwards. So there's a lot of ways that you can contribute to things without feeling the pressure of having to speak in a group."

5. Trusted relationships

Pre-existing relationships are important, so there is huge value in recruiting through trusted organisations.

"When you come through an organisation like Birth Companions, we're already in a safe space with them, so we trust them that you are also here for our best interests."

"I have automatically always had that trust with Birth Companions as they supported me at my birth.

They were my voice, they told me my rights which I never knew. So I feel safe and empowered with them."

"I had that rapport with them, so that's the reason I stay around. I feel it's a safe space, non-judgemental, no pressure, I feel our voices are important."

What do women need in order to feel comfortable getting involved in maternity research? (continued...)

6. Safe spaces

Research spaces must feel safe to women. They must be supported to feel protected from judgement, repercussions, and having their words used against them.

"The reason why I always still stuck around for all these years is because you feel like in a safe environment."

"I feel like, first of all, it's a safe space. I feel like if I ever bring like my thoughts and my experiences forward, it's never going to be used against me."

7. Clear purpose and value to work

Researchers must be clear with women about what the outcomes and outputs will be. What are the next steps? How will the information be used?

"I stay involved because everything we do, you know there's gonna be an outcome or it's working towards an outcome."

"Women want to know what's in it for them, because obviously it's giving up their time. You know, there has to be an outcome. It's about being transparent and saying, 'we want you for this research project and this is what you're going to get from it.'"

"I've seen a lot of people saying 'we need your help, we need your ideas', but there's no real reason to go. 'This is why I need your help because this is going to be the outcome' – that's the only way I'm gonna think this would be worth me doing this."

8. Feel included, genuinely supported, and cared for

Individualised support must be provided for women before, during and after every session.

"It's about caring about you as a person, which I believe is so important."

"We're not just another number on the research, we are actually part of it."

"How can we help make them feel like a person, not just a piece of research?"

9. Checking in before and after

It is very important to provide pre- and post-engagement care to all women involved in a project, especially as maternity research so often touches on traumatic experiences.

"It's how they support you during these conversations – every time we have any type of meeting – to feel comfortable, to feel safe. It's bringing back emotions, it's bringing back so much, so to know that somebody is actually gonna be there after, if you need them, I think that's just so important."

10. Follow up

Share findings, outcomes, publications and next steps with women in clear, simplified formats. If the 'final product' will not be available for some time, then share updates along the way.

"I think what it needs is a simplified approach to what the outcome is and what the next steps are. We quite often get the final piece of work, which is great if you're sort of in the world of academia and you're happy to read a research paper. But if you're not, you don't really know what the outcome is. So maybe a quick, jargon-free summary of what the research paper has deduced and what the next steps are."

Why do women get involved in maternity research?

1. To create change

"[Engagement work] is the thing that's helped me turn my negative situation into a positive."

"I think it gives you hope that actually we can make a difference, you can make a change and that there are people willing to listen to what you've been through and help make those changes."

2. To help other women

"I just want to help these women that are going through the same stuff because although they say things have changed, they haven't. And I just feel like there is so much that needs to be changed and I just wanna help wherever I can to change it."

"I just wanted to be able to put my experiences and what I'd been through to make changes for other women so that hopefully at some point they don't have to experience what I did."

"I wanted to help other women – I think sharing your story, giving your opinion, it always has an impact."

3. To make their voices heard

"[Engagement work] gives you that voice and it gives you the encouragement to express yourself, the empowerment to tell people what you've been through."

"The more I took part in research, the more I realised that people were listening to the things that we had to say, that there was no stopping me. So hopefully we can continue to do that, and inspire other women to get their voices heard."

4. A desire to 'give back'

This is a result of receiving support from trusted organisations or individuals that is unconditional.

"Birth Companions have supported me so much over the years, and so I wanted to be able to give my experience and to be able to share, as a person of colour, what my viewpoints are."

"Just giving back makes me feel good. And if other women don't have to suffer certain things that I have experienced, then that's great."

What are the barriers to getting involved in maternity research?

1. Trauma and anxiety

Reliving past experiences can be challenging.

"We are here wanting to share our story, but at the same time, keep it always in mind that it is traumatic. You're reliving stuff that's happened to you and that can go one of two ways. One, you can be desensitised to it, which isn't good. The other way is, you go down a trauma, every time you say it, you've got the trauma of reliving it. For me that's what the barrier is."

"When you're looking to do a research project, and obviously we're talking about trauma, then I think as researchers you should be looking at a whole trauma informed approach. If you're asking us really traumatic stuff over and over again or you want to know like first-hand lived experience, then your questions need to be tactfully written. There needs to be after care, before care, safe spaces."

2. Lack of safe, pre-existing relationships

"That would be my barrier – trusting somebody to give them what they needed for 'research' purposes and opening myself up to a private and personal situation regarding health and experiences."

3. Childcare

Women need sufficient notice to be able to arrange childcare, and some may need financial support in order to be able to afford it.

"It important that we know about all these events way prior, so you can make any arrangements, like if you have to deal with any childcare."

"I'd love to be able to do more [research], but it's just childcare!"

4. Uncertainty around next steps and outcomes

"What if I go through the trauma of reliving my story and then it doesn't even get used?"

"We've been to some of the roundtable things where you sit in a room with all these poncy people and they sit there listening, 'Ohh, thank you for coming!' And then you never hear from them again. You never see what it's done about it. And I think it is just, 'I have listened to those voices' and off they go. And to a certain degree I'm thinking, what's the point? If we're going to keep telling our stories, it's gotta be worthwhile."

Recruitment: Considerations for maternity researchers

1. Recruitment via social media

Recruitment via trusted individuals and organisations will often feel much safer and more appealing to women.

"I don't have social media, so I can't find things like that."

"Some women that are in, say, domestic violence relationships – they can't get to that through social media, maybe they're not allowed social media."

"Some people don't really use social media for this kind of stuff, because sometimes it can be too sensitive or you can't have access if you're going through certain situations."

"The younger generations that are going through things, they sometimes don't have that space to talk, so they will use social media. So it depends on what audience you're trying to capture and the way you capture it as well."

"I think it's about the content and the copy when you're doing social media – it is such a busy place. I could open my phone now and scroll and it will be endless. Unless something jumps out at me, I'm not gonna look at it."

"Mostly, if it's in plain text, then people would just bypass it. You've gotta be drawn in to actually pay attention. If you bring the scenario of what you're trying to say in a clip, and then bring the information within that clip after, that's when you're gonna get the audience to then be engaged."

2. Recruitment via posters/flyers in medical settings

"If I was sat in a GP surgery and you were looking for women to answer kind of personal questions – are you just interested in that, as opposed to caring? Is that what you're after? You just want the info about me and all of my personal information, that actually after that doesn't matter? So I think for me, I would inch towards going through organisations."

"If I was to go into a GP and I found a leaflet, I wouldn't trust giving them my personal information because I wouldn't feel safe with where my information goes, and I would rather be in a group that I know I feel safe sharing like all the confidential things."

"In terms of wording, if you wanted to continue with like leaflet drops and stuff like that, it's about empowerment. So it's making sure that the woman reading it can feel empowered to know that, if she's gonna share her journey with potentially a stranger, it's not just impersonal, there's a sense of empathy behind it. You want to know more so you can affect change."

3. Recruitment via trusted organisations

"With open recruitment, I personally probably wouldn't take part in it, but I would through a trusted organisation. We're here on a personal level and that's what a leaflet doesn't give you, it doesn't give you this one to one, listening to what you actually want to get out of your research, and that personal approach. So yeah, I think for me, leaflets, I think you're always going to struggle with leaflets."

"Research is quite niche, isn't it? So whatever you're after, you almost want to go to the organisations that are dealing with that area, so that you are getting specifically what you want out of it. But I think, in return, you then don't become tokenistic, because I think that has happened in the past, 'OK, we've listened to a couple of voices of lived experience, tick that box and move on.' I think it's about listening to the lived experienced voices and using it, not just ticking a box and putting it back in the box."